

A REVIEW OF AYURVEDIC VIEWS ON PEDIATRIC CARE USING LEHANA YOGA

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ABSTRACT

Lehana Yoga, defined as the administration of medicated substances through licking, is an Ayurvedic therapeutic procedure and traditional birth ritual intended to enhance nutrition, immunity, and cognitive development in infants and young children. This review aims to examine the concept of **Lehana Karma** as documented in classical Ayurvedic sources. The study employed a narrative review methodology, drawing data from authoritative Ayurvedic texts, previously published research, and relevant journal articles. The literature indicates that infants possess limited defense mechanisms against environmental contaminants and undergo rapid growth and developmental changes. In this context, Ayurveda advocates Lehana as a measure to support physiological development and confer nonspecific immunity against infections. Acharya Sushruta has outlined four Lehana formulations containing *Swarna* (gold) along with selected herbal ingredients. Acharya

Kashyapa provides the most comprehensive account of Lehana Karma, detailing its indications, contraindications, and various Lehana formulations. He particularly emphasizes **Swarnaprashana**, prepared with Swarna (gold), Madhu (honey), and Ghrita (ghee), which is also recommended by Acharya Sushruta during the **Jatakarma** (birth ritual). Additional formulations are described by Acharya Charaka, Acharya Vagbhata, and Acharya Harita. Overall, Ayurvedic literature presents Lehana as both a ritualistic and therapeutic intervention with potential benefits in preventing recurrent infections and supporting early childhood nutritional requirements.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Balopachara (pediatric care), Lehana Yoga; Swarna Prashana, Childhood immunity, Early childhood nutrition.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the traditional medical system of India, is rooted in ancient texts that advocate a natural, holistic approach to physical and mental well-being. Recognized as one of the oldest healing systems in the world, Ayurveda continues to be an integral part of India's healthcare framework. Its therapeutic modalities encompass herbal and mineral-based formulations, dietetics, physical activity, and lifestyle modification.

Children form the foundation of a nation's present and future, and their health needs differ considerably from those of adults. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 6,400 newborns die each day, representing 47% of all deaths in children under five. Since 2010, progress in reducing under-five mortality has slowed, with 54 countries currently off track to meet the Sustainable Development Goals related to child and neonatal survival. Major contributors to infant and child mortality include congenital anomalies, complications of prematurity, birth asphyxia, trauma, acute respiratory infections, diarrhea, and malaria.^[1]

Traditional medical systems such as Ayurveda offer valuable approaches that may support childhood health by enhancing immunity and addressing early-life vulnerabilities. Ayurveda offers comprehensive insights into the indicators of health and the practices essential for maintaining overall well-being. Among the preventive measures and birth rituals described in classical texts is **Lehana Karma** (licking therapy).

Lehana Karma represents a holistic approach to pediatric care, emphasizing the overall well-being of the child. In Ayurveda, this practice is employed to promote optimal growth and development by administering substances with both therapeutic and nutritional value. These formulations—often comprising natural, edible ingredients such as herbs and spices—are believed to enhance immunity, metabolism, and digestive capacity in infants and children.

Additionally, Lehana Karma underscores the importance of mental well-being by fostering emotional balance, cognitive stability, and intellectual development. Through its dual emphasis on physical and psychological nourishment, Lehana supports the comprehensive growth of the child.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study was to review the concept of *Lehana Karma* as described in Ayurvedic literature.

METHODOLOGY

This review was conducted by collecting and analyzing information from authentic Ayurvedic texts, previously published research studies, and relevant journal articles.

RESULTS

The birth ritual *Jatakarma* facilitates the newborn's adaptation to extrauterine life.^[2] Honey and ghee, due to their high caloric content, provide immediate nourishment and energy to the infant, while gold powder is traditionally believed to enhance protection and support cognitive development. With the initiation of the first feed, gastrointestinal motility and intestinal functioning begin to activate. *Jatakarma* also serves as an opportunity to assess neonatal reflexes such as rooting and sucking. Additionally, the ritual, accompanied by *mantra* (sacred chanting), offers psychological reassurance and emotional support to the mother. Acharya Charaka emphasized the importance of initiating breastfeeding as early as possible after birth, recognizing colostrum as an essential source of both nutrition and protective immunoglobulins. *Lehana Karma* is considered one of the components of *Jatakarma*.^[3]

Lehana Karma

Lehana refers to the act of licking or taking substances with the tongue.^[4] Children are particularly susceptible to infections, and Ayurveda prescribes various traditional methods to protect them from harmful environmental factors. One such method involves administering medicinal preparations along with *Madhu* (honey) or *Ghrita* (ghee), a procedure known as

Lehana Karma. This approach not only enhances the palatability of medicines but also makes them easier for children to ingest, making it one of the most widely recognized methods of pediatric drug administration.

Nirukti of Lehana Karma^[5]

The term *Leha* is derived from the root *lih* and the suffix *ghaj*, and it denotes the act of licking or passing the tongue over a substance.

Objectives of Lehana Karma^[6]

1. To support growth and development by providing essential nutrients.
2. To enhance immunity, overall health, and physical vitality.
3. To promote intellectual development and speech while providing protection against various diseases and developmental delays.

Several Lehana formulations, also referred to as **Balawardhana Yogas** (strength-promoting preparations), have been described by classical Ayurvedic Acharyas for supporting growth, immunity, and overall well-being during childhood.

Indications of Lehana Karma^[7]

According to the *Kashyapa Samhita* (Sutrastana), Lehana Karma is indicated in the following situations:

1. Insufficient breast milk

Breast milk is considered the ideal nourishment for infants, and nothing can fully replace it. However, in certain circumstances—such as maternal complications after childbirth, serious maternal illness, or inadequate milk production—infants may require alternative sources of nutrition. In such cases, Lehana Yoga (licking formulations) can serve as a supplementary source of nourishment, supporting normal growth and development.

2. Vata and Pitta predominance

Lehana Yoga is particularly recommended for infants with Vata and Pitta predominance. However, it should be avoided in cases of Kapha dominance. This intervention is typically applied for minor health disturbances in children.

3. Excessive crying in children

Some infants may cry intensely even after feeding, and many children show frequent nighttime crying without an obvious reason. In such cases, Lehana yoga can be considered—but only after carefully excluding any possible underlying medical conditions. For example, if a baby is crying at night and evening colic is suspected, *Shatapushpa* (*Foeniculum vulgare*) may be used as part of the Lehana yoga approach.

4. Alpa Mutra–Purisha

When children pass very little urine or stool, it often suggests inadequate intake of food or fluids—an issue commonly seen in infants and toddlers. Along with appropriate dietary and

lifestyle measures, practitioners may consider Lehana Yoga formulations such as *Chitraka* (*Plumbago zeylanica*), *Shatpushpa* (*Foeniculum vulgare*), or *Shatavari* (*Asparagus racemosus*), depending on the child's condition.

Niramaya but Krusha

This refers to a child who is free from illness yet significantly underweight for their age—one of the most frequently encountered concerns. If not addressed, it can lead to malnutrition. In such cases, combinations supporting **Deepana** and **Pachana** (enhancing digestive strength) as well as **Balya** and **Brimhana** (promoting nourishment and strength)—such as *Chitraka*, *Shatpushpa*, *Shatavari*, or *Bala* (*Sida cordifolia*)—may be considered. Lehana Yoga can be suggested to parents as part of this supportive approach.

5. Babies who do not pass stool for three days

It is normal for breastfed infants to go several days without passing stool. However, when a child has a bowel movement only after three or more days and the stool is hard, poor dietary habits may be contributing. Constipation often appears when a child consumes limited *Sneha dravya* (such as ghee or curd) and insufficient vegetables. With the increasing intake of processed and packaged foods, this issue has become even more common. While dietary adjustments are important, traditional formulations like *Triphala* (a blend of *Embolica officinalis*, *Terminalia bellerica*, and *Terminalia chebula*) or *Trivrit* (*Operculina turpethum*) are sometimes mentioned in Ayurveda as part of Lehana Yoga to help alleviate persistent hard stools.

Contraindications of Lehana Karma^[8]

The *Lehaniya Adhyaya* (the chapter describing licking therapy) in *Kashyapa Samhita* provides detailed guidance on situations where Lehana Karma should not be administered.

1. Mother's Condition

Three specific maternal conditions are mentioned. If the mother consumes *Sarva rasa yukta ahara*—a diet that includes all six tastes—she naturally receives balanced nourishment, enabling her to produce sufficient and wholesome breast milk. In such cases, the infant already obtains adequate nutrition through breastfeeding, making Lehana Yoga unnecessary.

This is particularly relevant for *Kshirapa* children (up to 1 year, primarily on milk) and *Kshirannada* children (up to 2 years, taking both milk and semi-solid foods).

However, in modern lifestyles, it is rare for mothers to consistently follow a diet rich in all six tastes, and the interpretation of *Sarva rasa yukta ahara* may differ today. The underlying idea is that if the mother maintains holistic self-care, no additional supplements are needed for the child.

If the mother's breast milk becomes *Guru stanya*—that is, excessively heavy due to Kapha dominance—it is considered a form of *Stanya dushti* (vitiated breast milk). This imbalance also affects the infant, requiring a Kapha-restricted regimen (*Kaphavarjita*) before considering *Lehana*. Therefore, feeding the infant with *Guru stanya* falls under the contraindications for administering *Lehana Karma*.

2. Mandagni (Weak Digestive Fire)

Mandagni is a state in which a child is unable to digest even normal, age-appropriate amounts of food. Despite adequate intake, the child fails to gain weight. Due to poor digestion, only a small quantity of *Ahara rasa* (nutritive essence of food) is formed, while excessive *Malamutra* or waste products are produced. This undigested food transforms into *Ama*—a toxic by-product of improper digestion. If this condition continues, the child may gradually lose interest in food (*Arochaka*, or loss of appetite). Persistent malnutrition increases susceptibility to recurrent illnesses such as *Jvara* (fever), *Atisara* (diarrhea), *Chardi* (vomiting), *Shvasa* (asthma), *Kasa* (cough), and *Udara roga* (abdominal discomfort). All of these conditions serve as contraindications. The primary illness must be treated first, and *Lehana Yoga* may only be considered once the child enters a *Niramaya* (disease-free) state.

3. Systemic Diseases

Lehana Yoga is also not advised in the presence of systemic disorders in children, as these require specialized management. Conditions that fall into this contraindicated category include *Hridroga* (heart disease), *Pandu* (anemia), *Kamala* (jaundice), *Shotha* (edema), *Basti roga* (bladder disorders), *Guda roga* (anal conditions), *Urdhvajatrugata roga* (diseases above the clavicle), and *Graha roga* (infections caused by microorganisms). Although not all these conditions are explicitly detailed in the classical texts, the underlying principle is clear: *Lehana Yoga* should be avoided in systemic illnesses, and treatment must focus on addressing the specific disease first.

4. Na Asatmya: Lehana yoga should be stopped if any specific adverse reactions are

5. Na Atimatra

Although Lehana is used to support immunity and cognitive development, this does not mean that giving a higher dose will lead to rapid improvement. When an appropriate and carefully measured dose is administered, the child undergoes a gradual process of immune strengthening and cognitive enhancement.

Various Lehana formulations are described in classical Ayurveda texts as well as traditional Sri Lankan medical literature. Some preparations contain only herbal ingredients, while others combine herbs with metals such as *Swarna* (gold). When gold is included in the formulation, the Lehana process is specifically referred to as *Swarna Prashana*.^[9]

Swarnaprashana—the administration of gold-containing formulations—is described as offering several unique benefits in classical texts.

These include

- **Medha Agni Bala Vardhanam:** enhancement of intellect, digestion, metabolism, immunity, and overall strength
- **Ayushyam:** support for longevity
- **Mangalam:** bringing auspiciousness
- **Punyam:** fostering righteousness
- **Vrushyam:** promoting vitality
- **Varnyam:** improving complexion and skin tone
- **Grahapaham:** offering protection from negative influences and microorganisms

The texts also outline benefits based on the duration of administration. For instance

- When given for **one month**, the child is said to become **Parama Medhavi** (highly intelligent) and **Vyadhibhir Na Cha Drusyate** (not easily affected by illnesses).

If Swarnaprashana is continued for **six months**, it is said that the child becomes a **Srutadhara**, meaning they can effortlessly retain and recall what they hear.^[10]

According to Acharya Sushruta, *Swarna* is given with honey and ghee as part of the *Jatakarma Samskara*, a traditional ritual associated with newborn care. This practice is

considered important for providing preventive and nutritional support to the infant, especially since adequate breast milk production typically begins only after the first four days of birth.

Acharya Vagbhata similarly recommends administering a mixture of herbal preparations to enhance *Medha* (intellect), using a specially designed spoon resembling the leaf of a sacred banana plant and made of gold. He also references the use of *Swarna* combined with other herbal substances during birth-related rituals.^[11]

Administration

According to *Jatakarma Samskara*, *Swarna* should be administered immediately after birth as part of newborn care. This form of Lehana Yoga may be continued for children up to one year of age.^[12]

Dosage

Acharya Kashyapa does not specify an exact dosage for Lehana; however, general age-based dosages for children have been described in the same context. Typically, **1/4th–1/8th Ratti** (approximately 15–30 mg) of *Swarna Bhasma* can be given daily without any toxic effects.^[13]

Lehana Formulations in Classical Ayurvedic Texts

1. Kashyapa Samhita

Composed by the sage Kashyapa in ancient India, the *Kashyapa Samhita* (also known as *Braddha Jivakiya Tantra*) is a seminal text on Ayurveda. According to tradition, Brahma conveyed this knowledge to Daksha Prajapati. The text provides comprehensive guidance on child healthcare, including breastfeeding, alternative feeding methods, nutritional foods, and the concept of supplemental nourishment.^[14]

Table No. 1: Lehana Yoga mentioned in Kashyapa Samhita.^[15,16]

Gritha / Lehana Yoga	Ingredients	Importance / Benefits
Swarnapashana	Swarna (gold), little water, Sarpi (ghee)	Enhances intellect, digestive fire, physical strength, complexion, and overall power
Brahmi Gritha	Brahmi (<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement
Mandukaparni Gritha	Mandukaparni (<i>Centella asiatica</i>), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement
Triphala Gritha	Amalaki (<i>Emblica officinalis</i>), Vibhithaki	Memory enhancement

	(<i>Terminalia bellerica</i>), Harithaki (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	
Chitraka Gritha	Chitraka (<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement
Vacha Gritha	Vacha (<i>Acorus calamus</i> Linn.), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement
Shatapushpa Gritha	Shatapushpa (<i>Anethum graveolens</i>), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement
Shatavari Gritha	Shatavari (<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement
Danti Gritha	Danti (<i>Baliospermum montanum</i>), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement
Gritha / Lehana Yoga	Ingredients	Importance / Benefits
Manjishta Gritha	Manjishta (<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>), Triphala (<i>Amalaki</i> <i>Emblica officinalis</i> , <i>Vibhithaki</i> <i>Terminalia bellerica</i> , <i>Harithaki</i> <i>Terminalia chebula</i>), <i>Brahmi</i> (<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>), <i>Bala</i> (<i>Sida cordifolia</i>), <i>Atibala</i> (<i>Abutilon indicum</i>), <i>Chitraka</i> (<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement
Kusthadi Gritha	<i>Kustha</i> (<i>Saussurea lappa</i>), <i>Vatankura</i> (<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> Linn.), <i>Pita Sarshapa</i> (<i>Brassica campestris</i> L.), <i>Pippali</i> (<i>Piper longum</i>), <i>Triphala</i> (<i>Amalaki</i> , <i>Vibhithaki</i> , <i>Harithaki</i>), <i>Vacha</i> (<i>Acorus calamus</i> Linn.), <i>Saindhava lavana</i> (rock salt), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement
Abhaya Ghrita	<i>Brahmi</i> (<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>), <i>Sarshapa</i> (<i>Brassica campestris</i> L.), <i>Kustha</i> (<i>Saussurea lappa</i>), <i>Sandhava</i> (rock salt), <i>Sariva</i> (<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> R.BR.), <i>Vacha</i> (<i>Acorus calamus</i> Linn.), <i>Pippali</i> (<i>Piper longum</i>), Madhu (honey), Ghrita (ghee)	Memory enhancement, protection from microbial infestations (Graha)

In addition to the previously mentioned formulations, *Kashyapa Samhita* also references other Gritha preparations, such as **Kalyanaka Ghrita** and **Panchgavya Ghrita**, for Lehana aimed at enhancing intellect. Although Acharya Kashyapa does not provide their exact compositions, these details are available in the *Charaka Samhita*.^[17,18]

2. Charaka Samhita

The *Charaka Samhita*, one of the oldest and most authoritative texts on Ayurveda, details the ancient medicinal practices of India. Beyond medical knowledge, it also provides insights into the country's geographical, social, and economic contexts.^[19] According to *Sharirastana* in the *Charaka Samhita*, a combination of Gritha and Madhu should be given to a newborn before the first breastfeeding. The text also describes several other Gritha preparations, such

as **Panchgavya Ghrita** and **Brahmi Ghrita**, which are recommended for enhancing a newborn's immunity and memory.^[20,23]

3. Sushruta Samhita

The *Sushruta Samhita*, in its preserved form, is divided into 186 chapters and documents 1,120 diseases, 700 medicinal plants, 64 mineral-based preparations, and 57 animal-derived formulations. It also covers the symptoms, pathology, etiology, and prognosis of nervous system disorders. In the 10th chapter of *Sharirsthana*, *Garbhiniyakaranashariram*, Acharya Sushruta describes the **Jatakarma Vidhi**, the birth rituals for newborns.^[24]

Swarnaprashana is also mentioned in this text. For example, Madhu (honey) and Sarpi (ghee) are combined with Ananta Churna (*Hemidesmus indicus* root powder), and Swarna Bhasma (gold powder) is administered to the infant using the little finger. Acharya Sushruta outlined four specific formulations incorporating Swarna Bhasma that aim to provide overall immunity, physical resilience, growth support, and enhanced intellect.^[25,26]

1. Swarna Bhasma with Ghrita, Vacha (*Acorus calamus*), Madhu, and Kustha (*Saussurea lappa*).
2. Swarna Bhasma with Ghrita, Madhu, Brahmi (*Bacopa monnieri*), and Shankhapushpi (*Convolvulus pluricaulis*).
3. Swarna Bhasma with Arkapushpi (*Leptadenia reticulata*), Vacha (*Acorus calamus*), Madhu, and Ghrita.
4. Swarna Bhasma with Khaidarya (*Murraya koenigii*) and Shweta Durva (*Cynodon dactylon*).

This formulation strategy highlights the importance of Swarna Bhasma in promoting immunity, growth, and cognitive development in infants.

4. Ashtanga Hridaya Samhita

The *Ashtanga Hridaya*, often regarded as the "Heart or Essence of all Eight Branches of Ayurveda," is one of the most significant classical texts of Ayurveda. It continues to serve as a foundational guide for Ayurvedic philosophy and practice, providing detailed instructions for maintaining health.^[27] Acharya Vagbhata outlines several formulations for infants and children aimed at enhancing **Medha** (intellect), **Ayu** (longevity and well-being), and **Bala** (strength).^[28,29]

Kalka (paste) of Endri (*Bacopa monnieri*), Brahmi (*Centella asiatica*), Vacha (*Acorus calamus*), Shankhapushpi (*Convolvulus pluricaulis*), combined with Madhu (honey) and Ghrita (ghee).

Fine powder of Chamikara (Swarna Bhasma), Vacha (*Acorus calamus*), Brahmi (*Centella asiatica*), Tapis (Suvarnamakshika or copper pyrite), and Haritaki (*Terminalia chebula*), along with Madhu and Ghrita.

Fine powder of Amalaki (*Emblica officinalis*) with Swarna Bhasma.

Brahmi Ghrita: Brahmi (*Bacopa monnieri*), Sarshapa (*Brassica juncea*), Vacha (*Acorus calamus*), Shariva (*Hemidesmus indicus*), Saindhava (rock salt), and Pippali (*Piper longum*). This formulation supports both physical and intellectual development.

Sarasvata Ghrita: Aja kshira (goat milk), Haritaki (*Terminalia chebula*), Trikatu (*Piper longum*, *Zingiber officinale*, *Piper nigrum*), Pata (*Cissampelos pareira*), Sigru (*Moringa oleifera*), Saindhava (rock salt), and Vacha (*Acorus calamus*). It enhances digestive strength, intelligence, memory, and speech.

DISCUSSION

Lehana karma employs ingredients commonly found in both Ayurvedic medicine and Sri Lankan traditional medicine. Key constituents such as Brahmi, Swarna Bhasma, Ghrita, and Madhu are frequently used in both systems. In both traditions, Lehana therapy is initiated immediately after birth as part of the newborn care rituals, and it is practiced primarily for its multiple health benefits.

According to Ayurvedic literature, infancy is a critical period of growth and developmental spurts that continue until around the age of 16. Acharya Charaka mentions a phase called *Vivardhamana Dhatu Avastha* between the ages of 16 and 30, during which growth and development are still observable. This period is considered part of *Balyavastha* (childhood). Lehana yoga is recommended for newborn care (*Jatakarma Samskara*), children under one year, and *Kumara* (young children).

Given the broad age range for administering gold, ghee, and honey, questions often arise regarding the benefits of Lehana karma in children. The effects of Lehana yoga may be realized from infancy through adulthood, as multiple factors influence a child's growth and

development. The appropriate age for administration should be determined based on the expected physiological benefits. Research indicates that gold may act at several levels, serving as a general health promoter or specifically enhancing intelligence, metabolism, immunity, physical strength, and complexion. As a general tonic, it can be administered to individuals of any age.

In modern times, children often have weakened immune systems, making them more susceptible to infectious diseases, which remain a leading cause of childhood mortality worldwide. Healthy growth in children is vital for national prosperity. Poor diet, improper eating habits, malnutrition, lifestyle changes, and environmental pollution all contribute to deteriorating health in both parents and children.

Lehana yoga can be administered to infants as young as six months to act as an immunomodulator, supporting the developing immune system during a period when infections are most common. It can also be given to children with immunodeficiency disorders, provided there is no concurrent serious illness. Pharmacological studies demonstrate that Swarna Bhasma, combined with ghee, honey, and other herbal ingredients, positively influences both specific and nonspecific immune responses in experimental models. Herbal components used in some Lehana formulations provide nutritional support and pharmacological benefits, enhancing immunity and promoting growth. They also stimulate peritoneal macrophages, which help protect against infections.

Since children have immature immunity, they are particularly vulnerable to infections and contaminants. The focus should be on supporting both physical and cognitive development during this stage while preventing disease. Lehana, as described in Ayurvedic principles, promotes growth, enhances development, and helps prevent infections. When administered in proper doses and combined with national nutritional and health programs, Lehana formulations can optimize intellectual and physical development, improve societal well-being, and prevent several illnesses. Its palatability and ease of administration make it widely used in pediatric care.

Certain Lehana preparations have specific therapeutic actions. For example, Acharya Kashyapa (referenced in Table 01) provided both general and specific formulations. Triphala or Trivrit Lehana is *Medhya* (memory-enhancing) and also softens stools. Shatpushpa or Chitraka Lehana is *Medhya* with *Deepana-Pachana* (digestive) properties, providing relief

for children with colic. Manjistha Lehana, being *Medhya*, can help manage Pitta-predominant conditions in children. Additionally, King Ravana emphasized the use of Lehana yoga for various childhood ailments, including cough, hiccups, excessive crying, and fever.

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda offers invaluable insights into the practice of Lehana, which holds a prominent place in both birth rituals and pediatric care. Lehana is believed to enhance the body's immune system, helping to reduce the recurrence of various ailments. Despite the depth and sophistication of its underlying principles, Lehana remains a popular and practical approach for promoting overall health and preventing disease. By combining ancient wisdom with modern approaches, Ayurveda guides individuals toward a more balanced, healthy, and fulfilling life.

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